

stunt disease may not be entirely due to BPH resistance; the rice variety Gangala is also resistant to the three known BPH biotypes, but it had a high percentage of seedlings infected with ragged stunt disease in the same inoculation test (see

table). Hence, Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 may be resistant not only to BPH but also to ragged stunt disease.

Experiments to confirm this finding are under way. ❧

Occurrence of water mold disease of rice seed and seedlings in Bangladesh

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A disease that caused rice seeds and seedlings to rot was found in seedbeds of the boro season this year. The causal organism is a phycomycetous fungus of the genus *Achlya*, commonly known as water mold. The species, which has not yet been identified, attacks sprouting

seeds and affects germination. Even if a seed germinates, the seedling soon rots or its vigor is reduced.

A few days after infection, a brownish, cottony, hyphal growth was found around the seeds. The disease was severe when the seedbed was submerged for 3 to 4 days during seedling emergence or after the sowing of sprouted seeds. Cold weather seems to have aggravated the situation. About 10 to 50% of the seed and seedlings either rotted or showed damping-off. Dry seedbeds did not have the disease.

A preliminary survey of seedbeds on the BRRI farm indicated that rice varieties differ markedly in susceptibility to the disease at one of the two stages (see table). Highly susceptible varieties were BR3, BR6, BR7, Hashikalmi, and Habiganj Boro II, IV, and VIII.

This is the first report of the occurrence of such a disease in Bangladesh. To prevent seedling loss due to this disease, seedbed submergence should be avoided. ❧

Evaluation for sheath blight resistance in rice

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From 1975 to 1977, efforts were made at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project to develop simple, rapid, and mass inoculation methods to induce sheath blight disease in rice and to evaluate germplasm and breeding lines in the field and in glasshouses. Preliminary results are reported elsewhere; this article reports screening methodology and catalogues entries that showed sheath blight tolerance in fields and glasshouses.

The pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* was isolated from affected leaves and sheaths collected from farmers' fields in a sheath blight-endemic region of West Godavari district, A.P. The pathogen was multiplied on shoots of the water sedge *Typha angustata*. *Typha* shoots are preferred to rice stem pieces because *Typha* stems are strong enough to withstand mechanical handling when inoculated and are readily available the year-round in irrigation and drainage channels. *Typha* shoots measuring 7.6 to 10.2 cm (3–4 in.) in length were soaked in 1% peptone water in 1-liter Erlenmeyer flasks for 7 days. The shoot pieces having mycelium and sclerotia were placed between the tillers in the central region of the rice hills, 5 to 10 cm above the waterline.

The field layout for screening included a normal 2-row observational nursery with

Reaction of some boro varieties and lines to water mold disease of rice at the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute farm.

Cultivar	Disease incidence (%)		Cultivar	Disease incidence (\$6)	
	Rotten seeds	Affected seedlings		Rotten seeds	Affected seedlings
BG 902	9.5	26.7	IR747-B2-6-3	3.6	68.9
BR 3	39.7	29.5	IR910-12-3-1-3	11.6	10.9
BR 6	4.2	40.9	IR944-85-1-2-1-1-2-1	19.1	6.4
BR 7	52.1	16.7	IR1103-15-8	38.6	42.5
BR 20-29-2	5.00	11.5	IR1514-E666	4.5	48.9
BR 43-11-2	1.00	3.8	IR1529-430-3	5.6	12.2
BR 43-11-3	0.0	0.0	IR2003-P17-7-4-2	18.9	32.2
BR 52-315-12	0.0	4.0	IR2031-724-2-3-2	47.00	41.8
BR 167-2B-3	4.0	15.1	IR2035-117-3	1.9	18.5
BR 167-2B-9	28.5	37.2	IR2038-158-2-3	3.3	16.2
BR 167-26-2-1	27.2	12.3	IR2053-87-3-1	20.8	16.8
Chandina	25.9	47.1	IR2053-160-3	90.0	8.0
Chandina/HR29-4	0.0	0.0	IR205 3-200-4	90.0	8.0
Chandrosail I	31.4	7.6	IR2053-362-1-4-4	95.0	3.0
CR 120	90.00	8.0	IR2061-214-3-3-28	5.9	5.1
Habiganj BoroII	3.9	16.9	IR2061-214-3-3-32	4.4	1.8
Habiganj Boro IV	8.00	18.4	IR2061-423-1	16.8	19.0
Habiganj Boro VI	3.3	15.1	IR2061-465-1-5	7.1	10.0
Habiganj Boro VIII	17.5	22.6	IR2061-628-1-1-1-4-3	16.7	46.3
Hashikalmi	29.00	6.0	IR2070-423-2-5-6	1.1	22.9
IET 1444	4.6	29.9	IR2070-414-3-9	5.7	56.2
IET 2845	5.7	8.9	IR2071-625-1-252	6.5	8.9
IET 2895	0.0	0.0	IR2871-53-2	3.1	29.7
IR8	11.6	11.2	IR3403-267-1	9.1	45.5
IR20	95.0	3.0	IR4405-451	8.9	35.2
IR28	7.6	10.3	Mala/Comilla	3.1	6.4
IR29	6.6	11.0	Mala/Habiganj	4.8	7.6
IR32	8.5	12.2	Mala/J15	0.0	0.0
IR78-177-3-2-2	12.00	5.2	Ratna	1.0	5.2
IR382-4-3-2	7.5	7.5	TN1	3.0	2.0

an appropriate check, 3 to 5 m long, spaced 20 cm within rows and 20 cm between rows. Ten hills were inoculated in each test row at about panicle initiation stage (60–70 days after seeding). Disease observations on the test entries, based on a 0 to 9 scale, were recorded at 3 weeks after inoculation and 10 days after flowering.

In greenhouse tests, the plants were grown individually in plastic pots 15.2 × 15.2 cm (6 × 6 in.) and were inoculated at around the panicle initiation stage. A minimum of three replicates were maintained for each test entry. For pathogen establishment, the inoculated plants were placed in humid chambers (RH = > 95%, maintained from 1600 to 0800 hours the next day) for 5 days, then transferred to glasshouse

benches. Overhead sprinklers were used from 1000 to 1500 hours daily to facilitate further disease development. Disease observations were recorded at 14 days after inoculation at 25 to 33°C, or at 21 days after inoculation at 22 to 30°C, based on the 0–9 disease severity scale.

In the 1975–77 wet season, about 2,000 test entries in the National Screening Nursery and the International Sheath Blight Screening Nursery were screened in the field and about 500 entries of the Assam Rice Collection were evaluated in the glasshouse. Those entries found tolerant in the field were also critically reevaluated in the glasshouse.

In our 3-year study no variety or selection was resistant to the sheath blight pathogen. But certain entries had low disease incidence; they had a few restricted lesions on the lower leaf sheaths and the basal stem regions. The entries having tolerance (disease score < 5) are listed in the table. Several of the tolerant semidwarf selections derive from gall midge-resistance breeding programs (e.g., progeny belonging to the series RP974, RP975, IR2071, etc.). Out of 500 ARC entries tested in the glasshouse, 4 rices — ARC 15762, ARC 18119, ARC 18275, and ARC 18545 — were tolerant of sheath blight.

Varieties and selections that had low disease scores in field and glasshouse tests at AICRIP, India, during 1975–1977.

Designation	Disease score		
	Field test		Glasshouse test 1977
	Wet season 1975	Wet season 1976	
<i>IRSHBN test entries</i>			
B 9c-Md-3-3	3	—	5
IR789-98-2	5	—	5
IR1103-15-8	5	—	5
IR1910-472 P	5	—	5
Guyana Sel. 60-283	5	—	5
IR2071-588-4-4	5	—	5
IR2071-588-4-5-1	3	5	6
IR2798-88-32	5	5	6
IR2843-26-3-2	5	5	6
BR-4-30-51-2	5	—	6
Remadja	5	—	5
Sigadis	5	—	5
Pankaj (resistant check)	5	—	5
<i>National screening entries</i>			
OR 42-10	5	5	8
RP 974-25-4-3-1	5	3	3
CU1 6475	5	1	—
CR 129-120	5	5	5
PAU 21-88-5	5	5	4
CR 149-3295-4-205	5	3	—
IR2071-176-1-2-1	5	3	—
IR2071-747-6-3-2	5	3	—
RP975-109-2	5	1	5
RP975-121-6-1-1	5	—	3
RP975-25-4-3-1	5	3	3

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Resurgence-inducing insecticides as a tool in field screening of rices against the brown planthopper

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Rice varieties and selections are usually screened for resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) in the greenhouse where 7- to 14-day-old seedlings are evaluated by the seedbox technique. This method has effectively identified highly resistant material but has been less effective in identifying strains with moderate and field resistance. At IRRI and in Sri Lanka, the reactions of some varieties have varied distinctly between the greenhouse and the field. Extensive field screening should precede the release of a variety. But several years may be required to obtain reliable data because BPH are distributed unevenly within a field and populations are often too low to evaluate. Even when screening is done in so-called *hot spots*, the pest's unpredictability can cause high expenditures in money, labor, land, and time.

The use of insecticide application as a technique in inducing BPH resurgence

was developed to provide evenly distributed and high-BPH field populations at about 80 days after transplanting. In insecticide evaluation studies we have identified insecticides that cause BPH resurgence. The synthetic pyrethroid decamethrin, as well as methyl parathion and diazinon, effectively promote resurgences (see table). The synthetic pyrethroid cypermethrin (NRDC 149), azinphos ethyl, and carbofuran also cause resurgence (the latter may be effective only where the BPH has developed resistance to the insecticide). In India, mephosfolan, quinalphos, phorate, and the combination of dimecron + nuvan have been reported to cause resurgences. Foliar sprays induce resurgences more effectively than granular formulations.

Our field screening procedure for BPH resistance starts with the planting of three or more border rows of a line, such as IR1917-3-17, which is susceptible to BPH but resistant to tungro virus (see figure). The borders are planted across each end of the test entries. Depending on seed availability, from 1 to 4 rows — each 5 m long — of the test entries are planted with 1 row of a susceptible check variety between each entry. The border rows are sprayed at a low rate — about 100 g